

VISUALIZATION IN BIOMETRIC FACE RECOGNITION

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Abstract.

Biometric face recognition is one of the fields of computer vision. The part of biometric person identification has been extensively researched. This resulted in a large number of algorithms used for person identification.

Keywords. knowledge, visualization, biometrics, face recognition, algorithms.

To effectively create and transfer knowledge through visualization, it is necessary to consider at least three perspectives. These three perspectives provide answers to key questions related to the knowledge visualization:

- What type of knowledge is visualized (object)?
- Why should this knowledge be visualized (purpose)?
- How this knowledge can be represented (method)?

Answers to these questions lead to a conceptual framework that provides an overview of the field of knowledge visualization. Perspective of types of knowledge that is visualized identifies the type of knowledge that is transferred. This framework distinguishes five types of knowledge:

- Declarative knowledge (know-what)
- Procedural knowledge (know-how)
- Experiential knowledge (know-why)
- Orienteering knowledge (know-where)
- Knowledge of related people (know-who)

With the help of visualization purpose perspective, the reasons for using visual representations of knowledge are determined. Objectives to be expected are sharing knowledge through visual means, creation of knowledge, learning from the visual representation, visual representation of past experiences for future users or mapping knowledge to be easily identified by experts. Methods perspective of knowledge representation structures visualization methods into six groups:

- Heuristic sketches
- Conceptual diagrams

- Visual Metaphors
- Animations of knowledge
- Maps of Knowledge
- Domain structure

The problem of face recognition can be defined as follows: If there is a set of facial images associated with the identity of the person (learning set) and the unlabeled set of face images of the same group of people (test set), it is possible to discover the identity of each person from test set. Many algorithms have been developed to solve this problem. This article will give a systematic overview of the algorithms used for biometric face recognition.

Visualization of knowledge offers solutions for the transfer and creation of knowledge, and emphasizes the important and often overlooked potential that researchers can take advantage of knowledge management: our innate ability to effectively process visual representation. Visualization of Knowledge also provides new ways of development for the visualization of information, because it expands that field in relation to other types of knowledge and other processes besides information research, because it uses information visualization methods based on computer as well as those that are not base on a computer. Future research will concentrate on usage of different aspects of knowledge visualization with a goal to help better understand complex fields of computer vision, especially face recognition and palm print recognition.

References:

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